

Eurodoc Statement on Open Science 2023

The principles of Open Science are an integral part of Eurodoc's mission. Open Science is an evolving movement that challenges traditional research practices by transforming the way research and knowledge are produced, shared, and used. It involves making data publicly accessible, fostering public collaboration, encouraging creative use of digital technology in research endeavours as well as developing more efficient ways for researchers to share their work. Open Science promotes knowledge-sharing among researchers. By enabling open access to data, methods, tools, and results of scientific studies – regardless of field or origin – it provides invaluable opportunities for early career researchers (ECRs). Eurodoc advocates the transition to Open Science by raising awareness about Open Science initiatives, by making recommendations on the implementation of Open Science for higher education institutions, European institutions, and other international institutions, and by advocating for research assessment reform that aligns with Open Science principles.

With increased access to data, resources, literature reviews and collaboration opportunities across geographic borders – Open Science empowers ECRs with the tools they need for success. Openness increases transparency while decreasing bias; it supports equitable and reproducible results that can be readily accessed by everyone interested. It also helps foster creativity and innovation within scientific circles as well as encourages cross-disciplinary interactions between diverse sources, which ultimately leads to more meaningful insights into a wide range of questions posed by society.

Eurodoc supports development and works on the following areas of Open Science:

- **Open Access to Publications:** Eurodoc believes that open access is crucial for advancing scientific knowledge, promoting transparency, collaboration, and innovation, thus helping tackle various global crises. Moreover, Eurodoc supports and favours diamond open access. We are committed to making research findings from projects that Eurodoc participates in as an organisation available to the widest possible audience. We encourage researchers to prioritise open access publishing venues, deposit preprints when not in direct conflict with scientific rigour, retain copyright, deposit publications in institutional repositories, adhere to metadata standards, and comply with public access mandates.
- **Transparent authorships:** Eurodoc recognises the importance of transparent authorship and encourages researchers to adopt best practices and initiatives that promote transparency, collaboration, and inclusivity in the authorship process. We encourage researchers to adopt best practices and initiatives that promote transparent authorship, such as Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT),¹ Transparent Author

¹ Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT), <https://credit.niso.org/>.

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Contributions (TACS) system² and ORCID iD,³ and to advocate for policies that ensure transparency and inclusivity in authorship.

- **Open Research Data and Materials:** Eurodoc is committed to advancing scientific knowledge through the promotion of FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability)⁴ when making research data and materials openly available. We believe that proper data management and preservation are essential for maintaining research excellence, which is why we follow established data management best practices. We also emphasise the importance of creating data management plans that thoroughly outline data collection, storage, and sharing practices. Eurodoc also supports the promotion of TRUST principles for digital repositories,⁵ which provide guidance on the long-term management and preservation of research data. We encourage the use of trusted repositories that are certified and assured for quality assured to live up to general open science principles and field-specific requirements by recognized bodies such as the CoreTrustSeal⁶. We believe that the use of trusted repositories is essential to guarantee the long-term management and accessibility of research data and materials.
- **Transparency of Research Data:** Eurodoc advocates a systematic screening of research data akin to plagiarism checkers⁷. Such a screening could limit errors, increase accuracy and feasibility, and prevent misinformation. The responsibility of implementing such a screening must be shared by all relevant actors, and should not be solely placed at publishers and reviewers.
- **Open Reproducible Research:** Eurodoc understands that ensuring reproducibility is fundamental to advancing scientific knowledge and contributing to the broader scientific community. To uphold this principle, we are committed to promoting the adoption of Open Science practices that enable replication and reuse by others. These practices include, but are not limited to, the provision of open data, open code, detailed documentation of research methodology, version control systems, reproducible reports, and proper attribution.
- **Open Software and Open Source:** Eurodoc is committed to promoting and raising awareness about the importance of open software and open source policies in scientific research. Open source software is software that is publicly accessible and can be modified and distributed by anyone. We believe that it promotes collaboration and innovation in scientific research by allowing researchers to build on existing code and

² Transparent Author Contributions (TACS), https://www.nasonline.org/publications/Transparency_Author_Contributions.html.

³ ORCID iD, <https://orcid.org/>.

⁴ FAIR principles, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.

⁵ TRUST principles, <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-020-0486-7>.

⁶ CoreTrustSeal, <https://www.coretrustseal.org>.

⁷ To fix peer review, break it into stages: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-022-03791-5>

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share their code with the wider scientific community. Eurodoc encourages researchers to adopt open source software and make their code openly available. To ensure that open source software is properly managed and maintained, we recommend using version control systems and using open source software that is well-documented, has a clear development roadmap, and has an active user community.

- **Open Hardware:** Eurodoc advocates the use of open hardware when possible⁸. Open hardware refers to the physical tools and equipment used in scientific research, which can be freely accessed, modified, and distributed by anyone. It allows researchers to replicate experiments and build upon previous research and can lead to cost saving by avoiding the need to purchase expensive proprietary equipment. We encourage researchers to make their designs and schematics openly available (e.g., using platforms such as GitHub⁹, Thingiverse¹⁰, Open Hardware Repository¹¹ and similar communities^{12,13}, Zenodo¹⁴, scientific journals¹⁵, or Open Science Framework¹⁶). We also support the use of open hardware licences¹⁷, which provide clear guidelines for the use and distribution of open hardware designs.
- **Open Infrastructure:** Eurodoc is committed to promoting the development of open infrastructure¹⁸ and raising awareness about the importance of open science practices among researchers and policymakers. This includes advocating for the creation and use of open repositories for research data, the development of open source software tools for scientific analysis and collaboration, and the adoption of open standards and protocols for scientific communication. We encourage researchers to use open infrastructure to make their research more transparent, accessible, and reusable.
- **Citizen Science:** Eurodoc recognises the value of citizen science in advancing scientific knowledge and promoting public engagement with science. Citizen science involves members of the public actively participating in the research process, contributing their time and expertise to advance scientific knowledge. We are committed to promoting best

⁸ Providing hardware details openly has been a niche topic compared to open source software, despite offering similar benefits in many technical fields. This has recently changed by open hardware being picked up in the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), in [CERN's revised open science policy](#), among others. A good introduction for scientists is given in the [Open-Source Lab](#) book by Prof. Pearce, alongside formal training and support through e.g. [Elsevier Connect](#) platform.

⁹ GitHub, <https://github.com/>.

¹⁰ Thingiverse, <https://www.thingiverse.com/>.

¹¹ Open Hardware Repository <https://ohwr.org/welcome>.

¹² Open Hardware community <https://www.openhardware.io/>.

¹³ Open Source Hardware Association <https://www.oshwa.org/>.

¹⁴ Zenodo repository <https://zenodo.org/>.

¹⁵ Like Elsevier's HardwareX <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/hardwarex>.

¹⁶ Open Science Framework, <https://osf.io/>.

¹⁷ Such as the [CERN Open Hardware License](#).

¹⁸ Open infrastructure refers to the systems, tools, and services that enable open science practices, such as open access publishing, open data, and open source software.

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practices in citizen science, including the use of open science principles to ensure transparency, collaboration, and innovation in scientific inquiry. We encourage citizen science projects to adopt open data, open access, and open source policies, making their data, results, and code openly available to the wider scientific community. In particular we stress that it is crucial that citizens are properly acknowledged for their contributions.

- **Open Educational Resources:** Eurodoc recognises the importance of Open Educational Resources (OERs) and promotes their use in higher education and beyond. OERs are educational materials that are freely accessible, openly licensed, and can be reused, revised, remixed, and redistributed. We believe that they provide educators and students with the tools necessary to promote collaboration and innovation in higher education, enabling the wider dissemination of knowledge and increasing accessibility to educational resources. We encourage educators to adopt OERs, and to collaborate with students to develop and refine them to ensure they meet the needs of their respective communities. To ensure the quality of OERs, we recommend using established quality standards¹⁹.
- **Open Research Assessment:** Open research assessment involves evaluating research outputs using open and transparent methods, including peer review, metrics, and other forms of evaluation. Eurodoc believes that open research assessment leads to greater fairness and accountability in research evaluation and promotes greater collaboration and innovation across the scientific community²⁰. We advocate for transparency in all parts by opening up assessment practices, thus exposing biased or otherwise flawed outcomes. We encourage researchers to adopt open research assessment practices, such as using open peer review in various forms, publishing research preprints, and utilising alternative metrics to evaluate the impact of research outputs.
- **Open Science Policies:** Eurodoc is committed to promoting Open Science policies that enable researchers to foster transparency, collaboration, and innovation in scientific inquiry. We believe that Open Science policy statements should outline a comprehensive approach to Open Science, covering open data, open code, open access, open peer review, open education, open collaboration, responsible research, and research assessment. Our aim is to actively promote and advocate for the development of such policies on the European level and to closely monitor that all aspects are being covered. We recognise that such policies are essential for advancing scientific knowledge,

¹⁹ Such as the [OER Quality Standards Framework](#), which provides guidance on the development and evaluation of OERs.

²⁰ Research Assessment practices have received many criticisms in the past years, and the drive to reform has led to the establishment of the [CoARA coalition](#). Particularly sensitive elements within the discussions are biases, inequity, partiality and potential repercussions, which have been main reasons e.g. for the introduction of (double-)blind review practices. However, these increasingly prove ineffective to ensure a fair and unbiased evaluation.

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enabling reproducibility, and promoting a culture of openness and collaboration in scientific inquiry.

- **Advocacy for Open Science:** Eurodoc is committed to advocate for Open Science in all the shapes and forms described above. By such advocacy efforts we hope to help create a culture of openness and collaboration in scientific research, and we are committed to promoting best practices in this area. Effective advocacy efforts require clear and concise messaging that emphasises the benefits of Open Science practices. To support it, we encourage researchers to share their stories and experiences of how open science practices have benefitted their research, also by participating in events and workshops promoting Open Science. We also advocate for policies that support open science practices. Such policies can include mandates for open access to publications and research data, requirements for data management plans, and support for open source software and infrastructure.

Eurodoc is committed to promoting open research practices to advance scientific knowledge through transparency, collaboration, and innovation. We recognise the importance of Open Science and its potential to benefit the scientific community and wider society. Eurodoc advocates for open access to publications, open research data and materials, open software and open source, open educational resources, open infrastructure, and citizen science. By promoting these practices, we aim to foster a culture of openness and collaboration in scientific inquiry. We encourage researchers and research institutions to adopt open research practices and to work towards advancing scientific knowledge through transparency, collaboration, and innovation.

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Date of Publication: 2023-07-02

Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 25 national associations of early-career researchers (ECRs) from 23 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research and innovation in Europe.